

A Systematic Literature Review of Contextual Teaching and Learning Approach in EFL Speaking Skills

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 02, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: August 02, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Contextual Teaching and Learning Approach; Speaking Skills</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13187079</p>	<p><i>The focus of teaching speaking skills at schools isto enable students to have a communicative efficiency. To achieve this aim, Contextual Teaching and Learning (CTL) approachcan be applied, which forms the subject of this paper. Thus, this paper aims tosystematically review the literature relevant to the implementation of CTL approach toward students' speaking skills.Data were obtained from a book of Elaine B. Johnson(2002), the proponent of the CTL approach, entitled "Contextual Teaching and Learning: what it is and why it is here to stay", and journal articles published in the past 8 years, 2015-2023. The results indicated that CTL approach is highly effective in improving students speaking skills due toits teaching principles thatare congruent with human brain in which meaning is built by connecting subject matter to the context of students' daily life. Not only does this approach bring a positive impact on students' performance in speaking, but it also makes teachers more creative in teaching speaking skills and supports teaching and learning activities at schools.</i></p>

Introduction

Speaking takes a central role in communication. Despite of the importance, teaching speaking skills in the context of EFL classroom is not easy. Too often, to teach speaking effectively can be very challenging for the teachers. Accordingly, they require a set of theoretical and pedagogical principals that can be applied to the planning and delivery of lessons on speaking. Besides, they need to make use of various activities to get students speaking in class. The activities should be tailored to the students' speaking enthusiasm and kind of speaking they need to practice (Harmer, 2015; Goh & Burns, 2012). In other words, before teaching speaking skills teachers are supposed to make some preparation to suit the students' needs.

When the students speak, they encounter some problems related to linguistics, affective and psychological factors such as lack of vocabulary, less of confidence, fear of making mistakes, bad pronunciation, poor grammar mastery, mother tongue interference, low motivation, and inhibition (Widyasworo, 2019). They have to consider many things too (e.g., context, interlocutor and culture). Therefore, in order to be competent in speaking students require to apply various skills and knowledge that are culturally and socially relevant, appropriate and comprehensible to their interlocutors (Burns, 2016). It means, when a speaker speaks, the skills and knowledge he applies should be appropriate and easy to understand and can be accepted culturally and socially by the listeners.

Considering the above problems, teachers need to apply an approach that can answer the above challenges. Contextual Teaching and Learning (CTL) has been used for years and got a positive response among educators. It is teaching learning concept that suggests the students to apply what they have learned into their real-life experiences. CTL is the development of critical thinking skills that occur while the students process knowledge in such a way that it makes sense to them in their own memory, experience, and response. CTL approach assumes that the mind naturally seeks meaning in context by searching for relationships that make sense and appear useful (Johnson, 2002). Therefore, it brings a positive impact on students' speaking performance.

CTL approach allows students to have experiential learning in which knowledge is obtained from the combination of grasping and transforming the experience. Getting three principles (interdependence, differentiation, self-organization) and eight components (making meaningful connection, doing significant work, self-regulated learning, collaborating, critical and creative thinking, nurturing the individual, reaching high standard, using authentic assessment) reflected into teaching strategies makes CTL powerful when applied in English language teaching. Hence, this study explores further what makes CTL effective in teaching speaking skills? It aims to systematically review the literature pertaining to CTL approach in teaching speaking skills, how it works, and why it works.

Research Method

This study applied library research method involving defining research topic, searching supporting information, determining research scope, searching and finding resources, organizing resources, taking notes, reviewing, reorganizing notes, and writing and revising the paper. A book written by the proponent of Contextual Teaching and Learning Approach, Elaine B. Johnson (2002) entitled "Contextual Teaching and Learning: what it is and why it is here to stay" was used as a primary data to provide insightful information on how CTL works. Secondary data, furthermore, were obtained from articles journal published in the past 8 years (2015-2023) answered the question on reasons for CTL efficacy in teaching speaking skills. Content analysis method was used in analyzing the data while the results were presented descriptively.

Findings and Discussion

1. *How does Contextual Teaching and Learning Approach work?*

Contextual Teaching and Learning is an approach which combines concept and practice. It successfully leads students to have a pathway of academic excellence due to its system that encompasses the whole aspects of learning as the way nature works (Johnson, 2002). If traditional method emphasizes students to acquire and manipulate the content through memorizing facts, events, figures, etc., CTL engages them in significant activities by making connection between the subject content and their real-life situations. As a result, the students can see the meaning of the learning.

System of CTL is compatible with human brain. It stimulates neurons to form pathways to express meaning. Johnson (2002, p.26) argues, "CTL is a brain-compatible system of instruction that generates meaning by linking academic content with the context of a student's daily life." Because the context provides brain with information that shapes its physical structure, students retain what they study and place it the long-term memory. Once the brain understands what it studies, the students will not forget the learning because it means something to them.

She also points out that the system reflects three scientific principles; they are the principle of interdependence, the principle of differentiation, and the principle of self-organization. Through the principle of interdependence students can share experiences in a learning environment. This principle also allows students to collaborate, to think creatively and critically, to engage in hands-on learning, to do significant tasks that benefit others, and to use assessment method that link learning with the real world. Furthermore, the principle of differentiation promotes uniqueness, diversity and creativity.

Thinking that students are heterogeneous, the CTL system gives them prolonged and concentrated individual attention. Therefore, CTL teacher should respond to students' particular needs and aspirations. In addition, the principle of self-organization allows students to have self-ordering, self-maintaining, and self-conscious. These help students achieve academic success and career skills as well as character development by connecting school work with their own basic knowledge and experience. She identifies eight components of CTL as follows.

First, CTL makes a meaningful connection. Students can learn the materials that make sense to them because the materials itself are gained based on their real-life context. Making connection to find meaning increases knowledge and deepens insight. Second, CTL allows the students to do significant work by relating what the materials have gained in the school and also in the various contexts that still exist in real world. CTL also allows the students to have self-regulated learning by creating the students an opportunity to have learning regularly so that they can get the knowledge as much as possible.

Furthermore, CTL provides a chance for collaboration through group discussion and sharing session. It also promotes critical and creative thinking. Besides, it nurtures the individuals to respect adult people who mostly have more experience from whom they can get some help. Helping students to reach high academic standards is the heart of matter for the CTL. By relating high standard as the characteristics of contextual teaching and learning, it can motivate the students to have more frequency of studying. CTL makes learning objectives clear and explicit and infuses them into every task.

In addition, CTL uses authentic assessment. The use of authentic assessment is useful in order to get the meaningful purposes. Authentic assessment invites students to use academic knowledge in a real-world context for a significant purpose. By doing the authentic tasks, students are challenged to achieve a significant result. As a result, they can achieve success in academic life. In short, with its eight components CTL help students gain better performance both in academic and personality, and this is an ultimate goal the teachers expect to have from teaching and learning process.

The CTL helps students make connections with both internal and external context. Therefore, the CTL is also called experiential learning, real world education, active learning, learner centered instruction and learning-in-context as "they begin with their existing knowledge, past experiences, and other current classes or situations" (Berns & Erickson, 2001, p.22) and conduct activities in such external contexts as the school, home, workplace, and the internet. These experiences result in a deeper understanding so that students are more likely

to retain competencies for a longer period of time and be able to apply them in appropriate ways at appropriate times in the future.

In a CTL learning environment, students discover meaningful relationships between abstract ideas and practical applications in a real-world context. Students internalize concepts through discovery, reinforcement, and interrelationships. Contextual Teaching and Learning creates a team, whether in or out of the classroom. CTL encourages educators to design learning environments that incorporate many forms of experience to achieve the desired outcomes. Simply placing a student in a “real-world” context does not guarantee a learning experience. Effective contextual learning results from a complex interaction of teaching methods, content, situation, and timing.

Implementation of CTL may not require drastic changes in practice for all teachers. It may require enhancement of practice in only one characteristic. Continual use and reflection on CTL processes broadens and deepens teachers’ knowledge and ability to facilitate learning as pointed out by (Cirocki & Widodo, 2019) that reflection and reflective practice provides the chance for teachers to assess their own teaching knowledge and practice. For CTL to be successful for all students, each teacher should draw upon her/his expertise when considering means of enhancing CTL practices and making them work in their classrooms.

Teaching speaking skills through CTL can be successfully done because the CTL relates to how the students learn (learning styles). Context gives meaning, relevance, and usefulness to learning. When the learners learn anything of significance and when they learn at their best, they are learning material that has meaning in their lives. It is more and more evident that when students learn that material, when delivered, is through the context of their lives, learning becomes more meaningful and enjoyable. In other words, the CTL succeeds in teaching speaking skills because it does not have the students speculate about what to do but to act naturally as they do in their daily life.

CTL creates a classroom where students become active participants rather than passive observers and a place where students are responsible for their learning. It emphasizes on the role of students than teacher. The students work more diligently when they are learning content that is interesting and meaningful. Once the students develop a personal interest in a topic or learning activity, they begin to provide personal encouragement to it and go beyond the specific instruction and expectations of the teacher. Teaching then becomes more enjoyable because the teacher simply plays as a facilitator, guide, controller, transferor, and evaluator to find the meaning and fact for students themselves.

Since the materials are gained through students, teacher allows students to find their own materials in real contexts and experiences. As a result, students are easily to memorize and understand the materials as well as motivating them to explore their learning. “Rather than abstracting ideas in rules that are memorized and then applied to other canned problems, teachers need to teach knowledge and skills in real-life, useful context and provide new and different contexts for learners to practice using those ideas” (Wong, 2015, p. 75). In summary, the CTL is based on cognitive learning theories. Thus, the students are expected not only memorizing the material, but also trying to implement the knowledge in the context of daily life.

2. *What makes Contextual Teaching and Learning Approach effective for teaching speaking skills?*

Several studies have reported the reasons for the success of CTL in improving students’ speaking skills. CTL effectively improves students speaking skills due to its five basic strategies such as relating, experiencing, applying, cooperating, and transferring (Suadiyatno et al., 2020). Relating strategy allows students to apply their background knowledge; as a result, they find it easy to express their thoughts and ideas. When the students learn to connect the material being discussed with their knowledge and environment, they will learn better (Indrilla, 2018). In experiencing strategy, they are going to learn by doing. They are going to explore and find many new things. These new things have labels that they can use in their sentences.

Next, the students are assigned to accomplish some relevant tasks to help them retain the concept. This strategy which is called applying strategy helps the students make sense new information by relating it to something they already know or have already experienced. They work together in small groups to solve problems (cooperating strategy). They share, respond and communicate with their peers; consequently, they can gain more understanding of the object being learned (Lail, 2019). The students are encouraged to create a variety of learning experiences with concentration on understanding not memorization in transferring strategy. The five strategies allow the students to perceive meaning because they engage the students’ emotions.

The concept of CTL promotes students to learn a subject matter through everything around them. Teaching and learning activities become more meaningful to them as the subject topic is closely related to their life experience and situation. CTL makes classroom more fun and enjoyable. As a consequence, students’ behavior towards learning gets better and it affects their performance in speaking. It not only boosts students’ self-confidence but also gives students opportunity to think critically (Hidayat, 2020; Sumarsono & Muliani, 2019; Halim & Muchtar, 2015). Put simply, CTL makes students involve in meaningful learning. Students can process new information in a way that makes sense to them because it fits in their frames of reference.

The CTL promotes learning community that helps students to learn better as they can help each other through sharing ideas and correcting mistakes and errors made by peer groups. This step makes mild students more confident resulting in positive vibes got from other students as learning is a social process which can be enhanced when the learners have opportunities to interact with each other in instructional activities (Sears, 2002). The authentic assessment of CTL also encourages students to become an independent learner (Aisyiah et al., 2023). The elements such as learning community and authentic assessment help the students to have more positive attitude toward learning. They have a significant role in the success of the learning process and are responsible for the students' learning achievement.

The CTL is not a teacher centered since students are more actively engaged in teaching and learning activities while teacher facilitates them to learn. It gets the students more motivated in learning speaking skills since they are given opportunity to apply their unique skills, interests, values and cultural background. When learning English, the students can build their own knowledge or concept using their individual skills, interests, and cultural backgrounds to discover meaning rather than relying on teacher's explanation (Wulandari, 2016; Annisa, 2015). Because the students' individual skills, interests, and cultural backgrounds are highly valued, they are encouraged to learn speaking skills.

To sum, the implementation of CTL in teaching speaking skills has a positive effect on both students' performance in oral production and learning behavior. In other words, using CTL method for teaching speaking skills impinges on the development of cognitive and affective of the students. The findings imply that using CTL method in teaching speaking skills brings some implications on theoretical and pedagogical practice. While CTL method is applied in teaching speaking skills, it provides context to students. Through the context the students can transfer new knowledge and understanding, develop analysis for their own deep learning.

Teachers, on the other hand, become more creative when using CTL method. Since the teachers are required to provide the context of learning, they have to think the best way how to make students an effective learner. Building schema through context not only helps students build shared knowledge but also creates a more holistic and accurate picture of learned information. They need the critical thinking skills to observe the situation, analyze it holistically and take into account many perspectives. A surface-level understanding is not enough in multifaceted world (Ilosvay & Ilosvay, 2014). Simply put, CTL Approach supports teaching and learning activities in speaking class.

IV. CONCLUSION

CTL is effective in improving students speaking skills because the system conforms to natural human activity that is making connections between academic content and students' real life. Besides, the three principals (interdependence, differentiation and self-organization) and the eight components of CTL (making meaning connection, doing significant work, self-regulated learning, collaborating, critical and creative thinking, nurturing the individual, reaching high standard, and using authentic assessment) correspond to nature's way which is remarkable power to improve students' performance in speaking.

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